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THE PROBLEMS OF PHRASEOLOGY AND PHRASEOLOGISMS

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the problems of phraseology in Modern English and Uzbek. It provides information about the specific features and classifications of phraseological units in compared languages.

Introduction

The vocabulary of any language is not only about creating new words, maybe, because of expressions, stable word combinations, both in terms of quantity and quality becomes richer in terms of with the "world" with such stable compounds the science involved is the science of phraseology. Phraseology is the study of phrases and this term was used by E.D. Polivanov in 1928: "I refer to morphology Syntax is related to lexis to use the term "phraseology" as a special science dealing with relations I found it necessary"¹. In fact, phraseology has been part of world linguistics for the past half century became the center of attention. as a result of a series of monographic scientific researches object was determined, research methods were developed, and this science is linguistics has formed its place among other fields. Nowadays, this term is used in the meaning.

1. The total number of phraseological combinations in the language;
2. The field, science, which studies fixed phrases.

In recent years, many languages have been used on the basis of materials as a result of large-scale phraseological research, phraseologisms are as follows is being described. A whole phraseology consisting of two or more components a stable language unit with a meaning is a phraseological unit or a phraseological combination (phrase) is called For example, in English a feast or a famine bad luck"]; think on one's feet "immediate response return"], put on the grill ["intrude", "torture"]; be (all) at sixes and sevens ["to be in disorder, to be in ruins"]; set on six and seven.

An example of this is expressions such as "taking a risk by putting it in the middle". In 1905 Sh. Bally was one of the first among Western linguists used the term phraseology. He uses phraseology from a stylistic point of view interpreted as an expression unit of the language.

¹ Umarxo'jaev M.E. Olmon tili leksikologiyasi va frazeologiyasi.- Andijon: ADTPI, 2010.-150b.

Researched phraseologisms in the 20th century to highlight the semantic classification of V. V. Vinogradov among scientists must make a semantic classification of the phraseology of the Russian language and this is it. Classification of many languages is an incentive to intensive study of phraseology. In this place, researchers of English phraseology N.N. Amosova, A.V. Kunin, I.I. Chernishyova, one of the researchers of the phraseology of the German language, Like A.D. Reichstein, M.I. Retsker, one of the researchers of the phraseology of the French language theoretical and practical research of scientists should be mentioned separately.

Review

Phraseologism is a lexical unit like a word. They are also in the language like words. It is not a speech event, but a language event because it exists ready-made. Phraseologism is phraseological in its own way, just as a word has a lexical meaning has a meaning. All paradigmatic, syntagmatic features in the word we can clearly see it in phraseology. At the same time phraseologisms with a number of features from words and free word combinations differs. For example, phraseologism as an element of the phraseological level, as a unit is an object of phraseology and phraseography. Forming phraseology the components do not have a wholeness of meaning, they are only aspects of form and sound is similar to the word with. Phraseology of the components that make them up a sign with a stable meaning, more emotional expressiveness, represents action. That is why the phraseological meaning is lexical differs from the meaning in several ways.

Most of the phraseologisms identity does not exist, that is, what this phraseology is expressing meaning cannot be replaced by one word and this meaning is a free word can only be explained by the combination. The scientific classification of fixed expressions in languages is, first of all, should consist of organizing the terms given to phraseology. In linguistics, there are various terms used to express fixed word combinations is being used. This situation arises due to the complexity of the nature of these stable word combinations. They are semantic, structural and functional are considered complex in terms of structure like stylistic, semantic, complex, syntactic function of speech and other principles classified based on As one of the traditional classification methods classification based on the structural-semantic principle is recognized. According to him stable phrases, pairs of words, idioms, wise words (aphorisms), divided into proverbs. Pairs of words are made up of units belonging to the same word group phrases with stable phraseological meaning are counted. back and forth ["again and again, consistent, to the smallest detail"]; backward(s) and forward(s) with the back"]; dos and don'ts ["according to the rules"]; between grass and hay [in the sense of "in youth"]; like open and shut ["simple, uncomplicated"]. We can use fixed combinations as examples of pairs of words.

Discussion

The term "idiom" is derived from the Greek language and means true, original represents Idioms are stable phrases that express events, events and objects components used for the purpose of description, the meaning of which constitutes them which does not come from the sum of its meanings and acquires a new phraseological meaning are stable compounds. Some idioms have the same meaning as another word can be expressed, but connotative meaning in idiom, stylistic uniqueness is not fully covered by this synonym.

The main features of wise words are their meaning, international the character is also determined by the word pertaining to a certain author. Wise words an aphorism given by the sages of the past and famous figures of our time comments, slogans, bites, quotes. This is what they have its characteristics are considered the main criterion for taking a place in the ranks of stable expressions. Although some of their properties become obsolete over time, they are a stable expression in the language will be preserved. Proverbs are also a type of phraseological units, from which the form and differs in content. Usually they are formed like a sentence structure which expresses brilliant thought. General phraseology with proverbs feature is that, first of all, they are structurally stable, have a general figurative meaning, and exist as an independent unit in the language. Analyzed above the traditional four groups of compounds are based on a single principle, pairs of words and proverbs differ in terms of structure. Both structurally and semantically, color is based on some specific principle makes it difficult to review. Also, a number of nodes in languages units-phraseologisms are not covered by this classification.

As we noted, the semantic classification of V.V. Vinogradov, created on the basis of phraseologisms of the Russian language, was of great importance in the formation of the classification of stable compounds in many languages. More specifically, it was proved that there are three groups of phraseologisms in other languages using the classification tool created by the scientist. According to this classification, phraseologisms are classified as follows:

1. Phraseological conflicts. This group includes language units that have a full figurative meaning, are not semantically divided into parts, and whose general meaning does not come from the lexical meaning of the components that make up the compound. For example, to kick the bucket, everything is at sixes and sevens.
2. Phraseological units. This group includes phrases that have an overall figurative meaning. Their difference from phraseological phrases is that the common meaning can be derived from the meaning of the components. For example, like a cat in a strange garret [in the sense of feeling uncomfortable, sitting on a needle].
3. Phraseological combinations. This group includes compounds that have a partially figurative meaning, have a semantic motivation, and whose components can be easily separated from the syntactic point of view. The components of such compounds can also be replaced by synonyms. For example, jerk (or snatch) smb. bald-headed ["to be rough with someone", "to take revenge on someone"]; come (or get) down to cases fix (or stop) smb's clock ["mute someone"]; be (or sit) on a cloud ["feel very happy"].

Chernysheva at the same time of stable phrases a complex that takes into account both grammatical, semantic and stylistic features developed principles. According to this, on the one hand, phraseologisms are from the word if the difference is determined, on the other hand, they do not have a phraseological feature

it will be possible to distinguish from stable word combinations. A fixed phrase must consist of at least two words. In this process, the components of the phraseology kept their balance otherwise, they may be deprived of this or that change. Below in the formation of phraseologisms of words characteristic of the ravish word group

Let's take a look at the position:

He realized that ...he was sailing rather close to the wind financially...
(Th. Dreiser).

...he's sailing near the wind with those large contracts that he makes
(J. Galsworthy).

He didn't buy a program - they were asking a shilling each for them and a man must draw a line somewhere(J.B. Priestley).

He was drunk... rotten drunk. A follow's got to draw the line somewhere (A.J.Cronin).

As can be seen from the examples, phraseological units are ready in the language are available units. They have two or more components. As a result, phraseology is a whole according to its meaning, composition and structure is accepted as a stable form. It can be seen that;²

1. Phraseological units are not created in the speech process, but they are ready in the language will be without;
2. Integrity, structure and semantics of its constituent parts constancy is a characteristic characteristic of phraseological units;
3. Components of phraseological units are two or more basic can have an accent;
4. Phraseological units are stable combinations consisting of separate parts that can be understood as words by the speaker.

Results

Based on the specific characteristics and internal capabilities of each language will have its own development laws. Stay in English the formation of phrases also has its own characteristics. It is known that the formation of phraseologism means the phraseology of this or that word combination which is assumed that it will acquire all the elements characteristic of stagnation. The reason for the emergence of new phraseology in English factors include: of new concepts that require a name appearance; replacing phrases that have lost their effectiveness with new ones need; the constant need for expressions related to the same historical period.

Conclusion

In recent years, phraseologists have been interested in the question of the ways of formation of phraseologism more and more interesting. These are language units content, including structural-semantic features of phraseologism with the fact that it remains one of the least studied areas in linguistics depends. Relations between semantic-phraseological variants of phraseologism. This is a summary of the main methods of phraseoderivation for clarification is also important. When it comes to the content of phraseologism, it is important to mention that phraseologisms do not simply name objects, actions, situations, etc., but describes them. It can be seen that the abstraction of phraseologism content level will be high. A special feature of phraseologism is that it is semantic the element of expressiveness is strong in its structure. Semantics of phraseologisms when we compare its characteristics with lexical semantics, the contextual feature of phraseology has not only an independent meaning but also because their semantic content is vivid and impressive differs. This feature of phraseologism is particularly important. There are seven main ways in which phraseologism can be formed in English. These are:

² Yuldoshev B.O'zbek frazeologiyasi va frazeografiyasining shakllanishi hamda taraqqiyoti. -Samarqand: SamDU, 2007. -108b.

- 1) acquisition of the meaning of variable word units;
- 2) mastering the meaning of stable compounds;
- 3) on the basis of potential phraseology;
- 4) individual-author phrases;
- 5) based on the plot;
- 6) homonyms as a result of a word game;
- 7) Formation of new FBs from FBs (phrase derivation).

The above six methods belong to the primary phraseological formation if so, phraseoderivation is a secondary phraseological formation. New at this phraseologism is semantic, grammatical and functional of the phraseologisms present in the language. It is formed on the basis of changes in aspects.

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